

Multicore and Manycore Design Approaches with DPDK

DAISUKE SUGISAWA ^{a)}

Abstract: Since around 2005, major processor manufacturers have shifted their architectural focus from instruction-level parallelism (ILP) toward multicore and manycore parallelism to achieve higher performance. Rather than relying on deeper pipelines and speculative execution, performance gains have increasingly been realized through thread-level parallelism (TLP). Consequently, the responsibility for efficiently utilizing processor resources has transitioned from hardware mechanisms to software implementations. ^a

^a Computer Architecture — A Quantitative Approach, 6e by John L.Hennessy, David A.Patterson

Keywords: DPDK, Manycore, Cache Coherence

1. Introduction

At modern data rates, the processing time available for a single packet is extremely limited. For instance, at 10 Gbps (14.88 Mpps), only 67.2 ns (-201 CPU cycles @ 3 GHz) are available to process each packet.

Under such constraints, even a single CPU cache miss (32 ns) consumes nearly half of the per-packet processing budget. Two consecutive cache misses would exceed the allowable processing delay per packet (64 ns).

In high-performance packet processing environments—such as those built using the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK)—the design must therefore minimize cache misses, system calls, and synchronization overheads.

On typical Intel Xeon architectures, socket buffers (s_buf) often reside in the L3 or L2 cache, and packet data can be placed directly into the cache through Data Direct I/O (DDIO) or Direct Cache Access (DCA) mechanisms.

The table below summarizes typical latency and synchronization costs observed on Intel Xeon systems ^{*1}.

The programmer is provided with a synchronous access interface to the memory hierarchy, while the underlying hardware employs complex mechanisms and architectural designs to ensure that these accesses appear consistent and coherent across cores and threads. However, while such abstractions simplify programming, application designers still bear the responsibility to understand hardware-level coherence mechanisms—such as cache coherence protocols—and to design memory access patterns that align with them.

Table 1: Internal Performance

Key	Value	Note
67.2 ns	201 cycles @3GHz	at 10Gbps / 14.8Mpps, time available for processing a single packet
CPU cache miss	32 ns	CPU cache miss time
CPU cache miss × 2	64 ns	Running out of available delay per packet
socket buffer: s_buf	fast	Hits L3/L2 cache in most cases
placed to L3 cache directly	packet → cache	at Intel E5-xx, Data Direct I/O (DDIO) or DCA
L2 access cost	4.3 ns	lat_mem_rd 1024 128
L3 access cost	7.9 ns	lat_mem_rd 1024 128
atomic lock	8.2 ns	17–19 cycles
optimized spin lock	16.1 ns	34–39 cycles
system call overhead	enough too big	a few system call invocations consume over 67.2 ns
synchronized-cost		
spin_ [lock/unlock]	34 cycles 13.943 ns	simple
local_BH_ [disable/enable]	18 cycles 7.410 ns	SW interrupt
local_IRQ_ [disable/enable]	7 cycles 2.860 ns	HW interrupt
local_IRQ_ [save/restore]	37 cycles 14.837 ns	HW interrupt + status

2. PGW

Fig. 1: pgw placed in mobile-network

¹ Xander, LLC. Shibuya, Tokyo, Japan
^{a)} daisuke.sugisawa.xander@gmail.com
^{*1} http://events17.linuxfoundation.org/sites/events/files/slides/net_stack_challenges_100G-1.pdf

we implemented a Packet Gateway (PGW) system, referred to as mixi-PGW, using the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) framework. The objective of this paper is to present and analyze several simplified pipeline scenarios of the PGW module built with DPDK, in order to illustrate key design considerations and performance characteristics of multicore packet-processing architectures.

2.1 PipeLine Stage

To efficiently handle a large number of sessions within a single PGW data plane, it is essential to design a processing pipeline that achieves a well-balanced functional partitioning across CPU cores while maintaining low-latency operation Fig.2.

Fig. 2: Overview of balanced pipeline stage

2.2 mbuf Pools

The receive (RX) functions cannot be invoked in parallel across multiple CPU cores, as packet reception for a given queue must remain serialized to preserve order and consistency. To achieve efficient utilization of the L3/L2 cache hierarchy, buffer pools are allocated on a per-NUMA-node and per-CPU-core basis, as illustrated below Fig.3.

Fig. 3: mbuf pools

2.3 Pool Mode Driver

Assign packet reception and Poll Mode Driver (PMD) processing to each NUMA node (or CPU-core group) to ensure locality of reference and minimize cross-node memory access latency.

Fig. 4: Pool Mode Driver

2.4 Mixed Latency Path

For scenarios that involve both low-latency and high-latency processing paths, a software ring is used to interconnect CPU cores, as illustrated below.

Fig. 5: Mixed Latency Path

2.5 mbuf Structure

A variable header start position offset enables encapsulation and decapsulation processing to be implemented with minimal memory copy overhead.

Fig. 6: mbuf Structure

We applied ManyCore - pipeline design to PGW encap/decap processing as follows. *2 Fig.7

Fig. 7: PGW Overview

The mixi-PGW source code is released under the MIT License. Users should be aware of and comply with the respective licenses of any linked dependency libraries.

It is our hope that this article serves as a practical reference for implementing custom user logic with DPDK, and provides insight into the architectural design and optimization of high-performance packet processing systems.

*2 <https://github.com/mixigroup/mixi-pgw>